

Enhancing wildlife trade monitoring in the European Union - No need to re-invent the wheel

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Abstract

Biodiversity loss is driven by overexploitation and agriculture, with global wildlife trade playing a significant role in natural resource depletion. The trade, encompassing live animals, plants, and derived products, contributes to species extinction and represents a major economic activity valued at US\$145–220 billion annually. The European Union (EU) is a key market, importing wildlife products worth approximately €100 billion. While legal trade has surged, illegal wildlife trade remains a significant transnational crime, disproportionately affecting endangered species and valued at US\$20 billion annually. Monitoring wildlife trade is challenging due to gaps in species-level data and inadequate regulation of many traded species. This lack of oversight hampers conservation and increases biosecurity risks, including zoonotic disease transmission. Global databases like the United Nations Comtrade provide insufficient species-specific details, limiting regulatory effectiveness.

The EU's Trade Control and Expert System (TRACES) offers a powerful, underutilized tool for wildlife trade monitoring. Originally designed for biosecurity, TRACES provides real-time tracking of wildlife imports across 90+ countries in 39 languages. Its advantages include comprehensive data collection, real-time monitoring, cross-border integration, species-level identification, automated data handling, and enhanced risk assessment. Studies indicate significant gaps in species identification within TRACES, which could be addressed through stricter enforcement and data verification.

Rather than developing new systems, the EU should strengthen TRACES enforcement to improve legal trade regulation, combat illegal activities, and enhance biodiversity conservation. By leveraging TRACES, the EU can reinforce its leadership in sustainable wildlife trade regulation, protecting endangered species while promoting ecological integrity.

1. Introduction

Biodiversity loss is primarily driven by overexploitation and agriculture (Maxwell et al. 2016, IPBES 2022, Hughes et al. 2023) with global wildlife trade - both legal and illegal - playing a significant role in the unsustainable use of natural resources (Bush et al. 2014, Díaz et al. 2019, Fromentin et al. 2022). This trade encompasses a vast array of live animals, plants, and derivative products used for food, medicine, as ornamental purposes, and exotic pets, pushing many species towards extinction (Symes et al. 2018,

Scheffers et al. 2019, Hinsley et al. 2023). Alarming, nearly one million species are estimated to be at risk of extinction due to these anthropogenic pressures (Fromentin et al. 2022).

The global wildlife trade represents a major economic activity, with an estimated annual value ranging between US\$145 to 220 billion. The largest trade commodity categories include seafood, furniture, and fashion-related products (Andersson et al 2021). The European Union stands as a key market in this trade, with imports of wildlife products amounting to approximately EURO100 billion, primarily consisting of fishery products, timber, and ornamental species (TRAFFIC 2025). The international wildlife trade has surged dramatically over recent decades, with the value of legal wildlife trade increasing by 500% since 2005 and 2,000% since the 1980s; part of this increase may also be due to captive breeding and/or ranching. However, this figure does not account for trade in timber or commercial fisheries, meaning the actual size is likely even larger (Díaz 2019).

2. The scale and impact of illegal wildlife trade

Illegal wildlife trade is particularly destructive, disproportionately affecting endangered species, such as elephants and rhinos, which face severe population declines due to poaching (Symes et al. 2018, Hinsley et al. 2024, UNODC 2024). While the illicit wildlife trade is valued at approximately US\$20 billion annually, making it one of the largest transnational criminal enterprises, it remains a fraction of the legal trade (INTERPOL 2023).

The Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES, CITES.org) provides a legally binding framework for sustainable international trade in endangered species between 185 countries. Despite covering an estimated annual trade value of US\$ 1.8 billion for animals and US\$ 9.3 billion for plants, CITES regulations also account for only fraction of the total global wildlife trade value. The EU remains a dominant player in CITES-regulated trade, consistently ranking among the top two global regions in terms of trade volume and value (CITES 2022).

3. Challenges in monitoring wildlife trade

A significant proportion of species remain unregulated due to gaps in baseline trade data and inadequate ecological monitoring (Stephenson et al. 2022). The absence of species-level trade data perpetuates a vicious cycle of regulatory inaction, as policymakers lack the necessary evidence to put forward conservation measure for non-CITES-listed species (Fukushima et al. 2020, Marshall et al. 2025).

Beyond conservation concerns, wildlife trade also presents biosecurity risks, contributing to the spread of invasive species and zoonotic diseases, such as COVID-19, Ebola, and Avian Flu. The increasing trade of pathogen-carrying insects as food further exacerbates these risks (Bezerra-Santos et al. 2021, Rush et al. 2021, Nawataisong et al. 2022, Li et al. 2023).

Currently, global wildlife trade monitoring efforts rely on various databases, including the UN Comtrade database, which provides aggregated data on value and volume (e.g. weight) (Drinkwater et al. 2021, United Nations 2025). However, this database lacks species-specific details and fails to distinguish between farmed specimens and wild-

caught, or convey their exact geographic origin, significantly undermining conservation efforts (Cawthorn and Mariani 2017).

In the United States of America, the Law Enforcement Management Information System (LEMIS) serves as a valuable tool for tracking wildlife trade in support of enforcement and conservation, yet it often categorizes data under broad taxonomic groups, lacking data granularity and limiting its effectiveness in species-level monitoring (Marshall et al. 2025).

4. TRACES: An existing tool for enhanced wildlife trade monitoring in the EU

The EU's Trade Control and Expert System (TRACES) was established in 2004 to enable real-time tracking of live animals, plants, and derived product imports for biosecurity reasons. While not originally designed as a wildlife trade monitoring tool, TRACES is exceptionally well-suited for this purpose, as it already integrates data across more than 90 countries and operates in 39 languages (TRACES 2025). By leveraging TRACES, the EU can enhance species-level monitoring, thereby strengthening conservation efforts and regulatory enforcement to the EU, as well as other associated European countries, such as Switzerland, Liechtenstein, Norway, and Iceland (Biondo and Calado, 2021).

Several studies on marine ornamental fish imports into the EU using TRACES revealed that one-third of shipments lacked species-level identification, underscoring deficiencies in data collection (Biondo and Burki, 2019, Biondo and Burki 2020, Biondo and Calado 2021, Biondo et al. 2024). Of the 26 million fishes imported between 2014 and 2021, approximately 8 million were only identified at family level (Biondo et al. 2024). This data gap reflects broader challenges in wildlife trade monitoring that could be easily addressed through improved TRACES enforcement and data verification protocols.

5. Advantages of TRACES for wildlife trade regulation

- 5.1** Comprehensive data collection: TRACES records detailed shipment information, including species identity, number of specimens, country of origin, and potential invasiveness. This standardized data enhances risk assessment and regulatory oversight.
- 5.2** Real-time monitoring: TRACES facilitates the immediate detection of suspicious activities, enabling a prompt enforcement of international regulations.
- 5.3** Cross-border integration: As a harmonized system used across all EU member states, TRACES enhances reporting consistency and reduces the risks of illicit trade. Furthermore, TRACES data align with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring a broader utility for conservation and policymaking (Wilkinson et al. 2016).
- 5.4** Species-level identification: While TRACES supports species-specific reporting, compliance with this requirement must be strengthened to ensure more accurate data collection and safeguard data granularity (Biondo and Burki, 2019, Biondo and Calado, 2021, Biondo et al. 2024).
- 5.5** Automated and secure data handling: The digital nature of TRACES minimizes human error, enhances transparency, and reinforces regulatory compliance.
- 5.6** Enhanced risk assessment: TRACES has already been used to quantify trade patterns and species-specific trends, such as in marine ornamental fish imports

(Biondo 2018, Biondo and Burki 2019, Biondo and Calado 2021, Biondo et al. 2024). Expanding its application to other wildlife taxa could facilitate better identification of high-risk species and targeted conservation efforts.

5.7 Supports conservation initiatives: Accurate documentation bolsters the EU's commitments under the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (European Commission, 2020). The EU boasts one of the world's most stringent legal frameworks for wildlife trade, integrating international agreements (CITES), strict regulations (EU Wildlife Trade Regulations), legal instruments (Biodiversity Strategy 2030, Habitat Directive, Bird Directive), enforcement mechanisms (TRACES, EU-TWIX seizure database), and partnerships with global organizations such as Interpol, the World Customs Organization (WCO), and the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC)

5.8 Facilitates collaboration: By integrating data across regulatory agencies, customs authorities, and conservation organizations, TRACES strengthens global wildlife protection efforts.

6. Conclusion

Rather than developing a new wildlife trade monitoring system (University of Oxford 2024) the EU should capitalize on TRACES, an already in-place, robust digital framework that facilitates species-level tracking of wildlife being traded. Strengthening TRACES enforcement and ensuring comprehensive data collection will significantly enhance the EU's ability to regulate legal wildlife trade, fight illicit activities, and contribute towards a more effective conservation of biodiversity. By leveraging TRACES, the EU can reinforce its position as a global leader in sustainable wildlife trade regulation, mitigating threats to endangered species while promoting ecological integrity.

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